

Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of 2-Amino-3-hydroxypyridine with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

H. L. KALRA*, J. S. MALIK and (Miss) VERSHA GERA

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

The proton-ligand stability constants of 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) and formation constants of its chelates with Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cu(II) have been determined, using Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti, in aqueous media at different ionic strengths and temperatures. The stability constants of the complexes follow the order $\text{Cu(II)} > \text{Zn(II)} > \text{Ni(II)} > \text{Co(II)} > \text{Cd(II)}$, which is in accordance with Irving Williams order.

Thermodynamic stability constants ($\log K_A^{\Delta}$) of these metal complexes have been obtained by extrapolating the experimental values to zero ionic strength. The values of overall changes in ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° accompanying complexation reactions have also been calculated.

THE stability constants of metal complexes with *o*-aminophenol have been determined¹. It was of interest to determine the stability constants of corresponding heterocyclic analogue of *o*-aminophenol, viz., 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP). Moreover, survey of literature reveals that no work has been reported on the stability constants of this ligand with bivalent metal ions.

In the present investigation, stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of some bivalent metal complexes with AHP have been determined in aqueous media at different ionic strengths and temperatures by potentiometric method.

Materials and methods :

A pure sample of 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., USA and its solution was prepared in double distilled water without further purification. Solutions of bivalent metal ions Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) were prepared by dissolving their nitrates while those of Zn(II) and Cd(II) were prepared from corresponding sulphate salts. All the solutions were standardised by gravimetric methods². Potassium nitrate (2 M) was used to maintain the appropriate ionic strengths (0.05 M, 0.10 M, 0.15 M and 0.2 M). KOH solution was prepared by washing KOH pellets with boiling conductivity water and finally dissolving it in CO₂-free conductivity water. It was standardised against oxalic acid potentiometrically. Nitric acid solution was prepared by diluting a calculated amount of the acid with conductivity water and standardisation against KOH solution.

Apparatus :

A digital pH meter (model pH 5651) manufactured by Electronic Corporation of India Limited, Hyderabad, with combination electrode CA-11

(0-14 pH range) was used for pH measurements. The pH meter was standardised with buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and pH 9.20. The temperature was maintained by running water with the help of water circulating pump from a thermostat through a double walled beaker.

Procedure :

The experimental technique of Bjerrum and Calvin³⁻⁴ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵ was used to determine $\bar{n}$ and pL values.

Three solutions, A : $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃, B : $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃ + $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand, C : $4 \times 10^{-3} M$ HNO₃ + $3 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand + $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal (total-volume 50 ml in each case), were prepared.

The concentration of the common ingredients were the same in all the cases. An appropriate quantity of KNO₃ (2.0 M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength.

The mixtures A, B and C were individually titrated against standard KOH solution (0.4 M). The pH measurements were done in an atmosphere of oxygen-free nitrogen at different ionic strengths and temperature. A graph between pH and the volume of alkali added was plotted. The three titration curves so obtained were referred to as (i) acid, (ii) ligand and (iii) complex titration curves, respectively.

Results and Discussion

To calculate the proton-ligand stability constants, the values of $\bar{n}_A$ were calculated at different pH values by noting v' from acid titration curve and v'' from ligand titration curve for the same pH using the following equation :

$$\bar{n}_A = \left\{ y^{T^0} C_L + \frac{(v' - v'')(N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + v')} \right\} / T^0 C_L \dots (1)$$

* Author for correspondence.

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANT OF THE LIGAND AND STEPWISE AND OVERALL METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS AND TEMPERATURES

Metal ion	log K _n ^H /log K _n	Temp. 20°					Temp. 30°	Temp. 40°
		μ = 0.0	μ = 0.05	μ = 0.1	μ = 0.15	μ = 0.20	μ = 0.10	μ = 0.10
Cd ²⁺	log K ₁ ^H	—	9.50	9.35	9.24	9.15	9.21	9.07
	log K ₂ ^H	—	6.01	5.89	5.79	5.71	5.74	5.62
	log β ₂ ^H	—	15.51	15.24	15.03	14.86	14.95	14.69
	log K ₁	3.48	3.28	3.19	3.13	3.06	3.12	3.01
	log K ₂	3.18	3.04	2.97	2.93	2.89	2.87	2.74
Co ²⁺	log β ₂	6.66	6.32	6.16	6.06	5.95	5.99	5.75
	log K ₁	3.58	3.37	3.26	3.19	3.12	3.16	3.05
	log K ₂	3.12	2.92	2.87	2.83	2.79	2.80	2.71
Ni ²⁺	log β ₂	6.70	6.29	6.13	6.02	5.91	5.96	5.76
	log K ₁	3.66	3.44	3.32	3.25	3.18	3.21	3.10
	log K ₂	3.04	2.98	2.89	2.84	2.80	2.82	2.75
Zn ²⁺	log β ₂	6.70	6.42	6.21	6.09	5.98	6.03	5.85
	log K ₁	4.36	4.05	3.90	3.80	3.71	3.77	3.64
	log K ₂	3.95	3.63	3.48	3.37	3.29	3.36	3.26
Cu ²⁺	log β ₂	8.31	7.68	7.38	7.17	7.00	7.13	6.90
	log K ₁	6.85	6.44	6.23	6.16	5.95	6.02	5.74
	log K ₂	5.08	4.57	4.38	4.21	4.02	4.20	4.06
	log β ₂	11.93	11.01	10.61	10.37	9.97	10.22	9.80

The proton-ligand stability constants were obtained from the formation curves so obtained and refined by various computational techniques⁶.

The following equations (2) and (3) were used to calculate the average number of ligands attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$) and the negative logarithms of the free ligand concentration (pL) at a particular pH .

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(v'' - v') (N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + v') \cdot \bar{n}_A \cdot r^0 C_M} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$pL = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n-1} \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{anti log } pH} \right)^n}{r^0 C_L - \bar{n} r^0 C_M} \times \frac{V^0 + v''}{V^0} \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

The terms used in equations (1), (2) and (3) have their usual meanings.

Metal-ligand formation constants were calculated from the formation curves obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL . The formation constants thus obtained were refined using various computational techniques⁶ viz. (1) correction term method, (2) pointwise calculation method, (3) least squares treatment (simultaneous equations method), and (4) least squares treatment (curve fitting method) and are given in Table 1.

The thermodynamic formation constants were obtained by the extrapolation to zero ionic concentration from the plots of log K versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ and are given in Table 1.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The values of overall change in free energy (ΔG^0), enthalpy (ΔH^0) and entropy (ΔS^0) accompanying complexation reactions have been determined using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz⁷ equation.

The value of ΔG^0 was obtained from the expression $\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln \beta$ and ΔH^0 was determined

with the help of an isobar equation

$$\frac{d \ln \beta}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H^0}{RT^2}$$

which may be rewritten as

$$\frac{d(\log \beta)}{d(1/T)} = \frac{-\Delta H^0}{4.57}$$

The values of log β obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $1/T$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 30° was determined and equated to $\frac{-\Delta H^0}{4.57}$. The value of ΔH^0 was thus obtained. ΔS^0 was then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S^0 = \frac{\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0}{T}$$

The values of ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH AHP $\mu = 0.1M$

Metal ion	$-\Delta G^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹ (20°)	$-\Delta H^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^0 cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ (30°)
Cd ²⁺	8.21	8.39	-0.26
Co ²⁺	8.26	8.39	-0.54
Ni ²⁺	8.41	8.39	-0.096
Zn ²⁺	9.87	9.65	0.86
Cu ²⁺	14.27	14.26	-0.36

In the initial stages of the titration, the ligand curve is shifted to the left (or above) of the acid curve due to the basic properties of the amino group which accepts a proton from the strongly acidic medium.

The protonated species formed dissociates in two steps as shown below :

Both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes could be studied in all the cases. It is evident from Table 1 that log K_1 and log K_2 values at 20° are higher than their values at 30 and 40° with all the metals indicating that low temperature is favourable for complex formation. The stability constants follow the trend $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$ at all the ionic strengths and temperatures. This is in accordance with the Irving Williams⁸ order.

All the complexes were found to be enthalpy stabilized. The negative value of ΔH° in the systems ensure that the reactions are exothermic. The entropy factor has been found to be favourable only in the case of Zn^{2+} complex.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Professor V. Yatirajam Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra

University, Kurukshetra for facilities. One of them (J.S.M.) is thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher-Fellowship under FIP and to the Jat Education Society, Rohtak for grant of leave.

References

1. "Stability Constants of Metal-Ion Complexes", compiled by A. E. MARTELL (Organic ligands), and L. G. SILLEN (Inorganic ligands). The Chemical Society, Special Publication No. 17, London, 1964.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1962.
3. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Hasse & Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
4. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
7. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VAS'L'EV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1960.
8. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.